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Overcoming Financial Barriers for making Transition happen

A proposal to retrofit privately owned buildings for energy efficiency in Frankfurt am Main

Jury Award winning project idea during the Climate KIC-PhD summer school "*Energy Transition in Frankfurt: Overcoming Barriers to Change*", organized by Making Transition Happen Platform of EIT Climate-KIC, Hessen. This research article has been prepared after summering detail findings of original report. Authors would like to acknowledge Climate-KIC (Hessen), EIT and City of Frankfurt for offering enormous supports; however this article only presents authors independent opinions.

Overcoming financial barriers for making transition happen:

A proposal to retrofit privately owned buildings for energy efficiency in Frankfurt am Main

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ABSTRACT

Reducing energy demand by 50% by 2050 is one of the two core components of the City of Frankfurt's "Master Plan 100% Climate Protection". According to this ambitious Master Plan, Frankfurt aims to reduce its current energy demand by half and to cover the remaining half through renewable energy. Since households account for 22% of Frankfurt's current energy demand, the achievement of the energy efficiency target largely hinges on private homeowners' ability to retrofit their buildings. However, homeowners' ability to retrofit their buildings for energy efficiency has so far been hampered by the high cost of retrofitting and lack of adequate financial resources. Despite the presence of some financial schemes designed to address this problem (at the national level), Frankfurt does not have adequate and coordinated retrofit-financing scheme tailored to its specific situation. We consider this to be a serious problem and major stumbling block in Frankfurt's effort to become energy efficient and thereby attain its 100% renewable energy vision. Against this backdrop, we came up with a solution that is capable of overcoming the financial barriers preventing private homeowners in the City of Frankfurt from retrofitting their buildings for energy efficiency. Our financial solution is designed in such a way that homeowners virtually pay nothing to get their building retrofitted. The scheme will enable homeowners to get a government subsidy plus long term, low interest rate retroFrank loans, which will be paid back through energy saving over time.

Key words: Climate protection, Energy transition, Building Retrofitting, Frankfurt

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1. INTRODUCTION

Reducing energy demand by 50% by 2050 is one of the two core components of the City of Frankfurt's "Master Plan 100% Climate Protection". According to this ambitious Master Plan, Frankfurt aims to reduce its current energy demand by half and to cover the remaining half through renewable energy. The building sector offers an enormous opportunity in relation to the energy efficiency target. In 2013, households account for 22% of the energy demand in Frankfurt. As found out by a 2008 study commissioned by the City of Frankfurt (e.g. Energy Action Plan and CO₂ Inventory for Frankfurt am Main), increased efficiency in the use of energy by private households for heat and electricity could reduce the City of Frankfurt's CO₂ emission by 4.2% and 3.4%, respectively, within 10 years. By eliminating wasted energy, energy efficiency retrofit could reduce Frankfurt's energy demand significantly and accelerate the attainment of its vision 2050. A comprehensive retrofitting may also help buildings produce more energy than they consume. independent

However, retrofitting buildings for energy efficiency faces numerous challenges. In the case of Frankfurt, financing is the most prominent barrier for private homeowners to retrofit or replace old building systems with new energy saving technologies or processes. Retrofitting buildings for energy efficiency requires a high initial capital, but many homeowners do not have the necessary capital. Financial loans are one of the traditional instruments of overcoming such barriers, but the existing retrofit loan schemes tend to be less attractive for homeowners. This largely stems from the fact that energy efficiency retrofit investments have long payback periods. The financing problem is further exacerbated by the homeowners' credit unworthiness. This has led to the limited use of the retrofit loans provided by the KfW, which provides low interest, long-term loans for the purpose of retrofitting projects throughout Germany. Another equally daunting challenge is the so-called "split incentive" or "landlord/tenant dilemma". This is a situation that may arise when the occupier of a building does not own it. In such situations, while the owner is the one who pays for the energy efficiency retrofit, the benefits - from energy saving - tend to go to the tenant. Tackling this problem has proven to be difficult for quite some time. Moreover, energy efficiency retrofit suffers from lack of sufficient public support/incentives. Unlike other countries, such as Italy and the United States, Germany/Frankfurt does not have a public subsidy scheme, which is adequate enough to address the lack of economic incentive

for energy efficiency retrofitting. The attainment of Frankfurt's 50% energy reduction target calls for the creation of a retrofit financial scheme with economic incentives and opportunities for private homeowners to retrofit their buildings for energy efficiency.

Against this backdrop, we started our work by identifying and examining the aforementioned financial problems as well as the shortcomings of the existing financial schemes in detail. For this purpose we interviewed three officials from the municipality (i.e. executive of Energiereferat, member of Climate-KIC Pioneer programme, Mater Plan Project Lead), two from the financial institutions, one homeowner currently retrofitting his building in Frankfurt-Hoerst, four randomly chosen homeowners and tenants. Most of the interviews were carried out in person.ⁱ We have also critically analysed case studies (conducted both in the context of Frankfurt and other cities) on overcoming barriers in energy transition in general and retrofitting buildings for energy efficiency in particular.

This study used the information obtained through the above noted methods to analyse the interaction and role of the different stakeholders in the retrofit financing market. In particular, we conducted a system analysis of the relationship among financial institutions, the municipality and its agencies, contractors, and homeowners as well as tenants. Our analysis reveals that despite the existence of some financial schemes, retrofitting buildings in the City of Frankfurt still suffers from lack of effective, harmonized, flexible, and attractive financing scheme.

2. BACKGROUND

This section seeks to highlight the key facts and figure about Frankfurt's building stocks. Most significant background on retrofitting potentials of residential building stocks can be summarised from an IFEU (2009) study as mentioned:

2.1 High Share of Residential Building Stocks.

Like any other city in the world, the City of Frankfurt has different types of building stocks (e.g residential, industrial, office). The residential sector accounts for a major share of the building stock in Frankfurt about 25,000,000 where only 15 % new addition of residential building stocks in last two decades has observed compare to no-residential building stocks. Therefore, a retrofitting program aimed at the residential building stock may have long-term

and significant contribution to the attainment of Frankfurt's ambitious goal of reducing energy demand by 50% by 2050.

2.2 Dilapidated building.

A recent study by Fraunhofer IBP has demonstrated that the major share of the building stocks in some urban district of Frankfurt is more than 90 years old. The dilapidated condition of Frankfurt's building stocks suggests that - notwithstanding the need for retrofitting buildings for energy efficiency - there is already an immediate need for renovation. This makes retrofitting even more appealing especially to private homeowners.

2.3 Higher residential heat demand.

The aforementioned study by the Fraunhofer IBP further identified that the residential building sector has high heat demand in many urban districts of Frankfurt.

2.4 HH Economic potential (Heat use).

All other energy carriers other than electricity are referred to heating use. The final energy consumption is here at the private households in 2005, about 3,966 GWh, the CO₂ emissions are 1,024,000 tons. Without additional construction or applications, the private household has the economic potential up to 27% in 10 years.

2.5 HH Economic potential (Electricity use).

The power consumption and the CO₂ emissions of households in 2005 was about 843 GWh, or 605,000 tonnes. The power-efficiency potential of private households, which could be implemented economically over the next 10 or 20 years.

3. SYSTEM ANALYSIS OF EXISTING ACTOR

The building retrofit is one of the significant sub-components of complex urban building system transition. There are diverse functionalities and relationships, which are critical for any action aimed at ensuring energy efficiency. The dynamic complexity is also need to be considered to deal with the barrier of building level energy efficiency measures.

To this end, we have created an actor mapping tools that illustrate the relationships among the key players within the retrofit financing market, in a simplified way (see figure 1 below).

This mapping product is not only visualizing the existing relations of key stakeholders, but also helpful to find out the potential solutions to overcome some of the financial barriers.

Figure 1: Existing complex actor map

Source: Authors own (map as mentioned Sikder et al., 2015), according to results of document analysis and KI interview (2014)

The city council of Frankfurt which does not only own the vision for its citizen to become a climate pioneer but also wants to maintain its competitiveness at global level, is the principal actor in the retrofit financing market. The city council is responsible for managing the transition process and is expected to contribute towards the attainment of the master plan by taking all the necessary measures within its mandate. They demonstrated the ability to respond to global climate change challenges over the past 20 years. As one of the financial capitals of Europe – often called Manhattan, Frankfurt has huge potential to keep its committed progress towards sustainability and resilience. Another noteworthy advantage of city council to make enormous contribution to the transition process as they own the city’s largest housing company (i.e. ABG) and utility agency (i.e. Mainova). ABG is one of the major owners of the existing building stocks (about 25%) in Frankfurt. It is

working very closely with utility agencies and the City Council in several areas including energy transition. We assume that they are also in a good position to bring major housing related actors together mainly because of their good reputation in the business and well connectedness in the region. Mainova is also doing well in business terms and is actively involved within the transition process of Frankfurt city. It has already carried out some demonstration projects for energy generation and savings in different part of the city in co-operation with others partners. ABGnova -a joint platform - which is working in co-operation between ABG Mainova. It is established to serve as an innovation agent for energy, housing and transport issue in Frankfurt city. It also provides different advisory services to the citizens of Frankfurt. This platform could be used as a potential institutional framework for the administration of future retrofit financing scheme.

Private-building owners are the major end users, target group and the deciding actors in the context of any building-retrofitting program. They face different kinds of barriers when it comes to retrofitting financing, relocation during the construction work. They are also the main victims of the above mentioned landlord/tenant dilemma. They have both money flow and materials flow between the capital providers, contractors and tenants. Capital providers include all kinds of funding agencies (e.g. KfW, Commercial banks), long terms investors (e.g. insurance companies, pension funds, social responsible mutual funds) and individual investors. They are one of the most prominent potential agents to provide financial resources needed for realizing Frankfurt's vision 2050. Contractors include all kinds of technical support and service providers. That is, construction companies, appliance suppliers, engineers, designers and others. They are acting as the top most potential supporters for retrofitting buildings for energy efficiency. Tenants are the end users who are often in the best position to benefit from building retrofitting activities. In most cases, they are not making any kind of investments and even may not want to pay increased rents for retrofitted buildings. However, this group may also contribute by investing on some joint financial arrangements with homeowner and building retrofitting funds if there is an attractive and well thought out package in place.

4. FINANCIAL BARRIERS

Several barriers prevent private homeowners from retrofitting their buildings for energy efficiency in Frankfurt. However, as already noted, our project focuses only on overcoming the financial barriers. In this regard, our investigation, conducted through questioner and interviews with relevant stakeholders, suggests that the following financial barriers are the most prominent ones in Frankfurt's retrofitting market:

4.1 High initial cost for homeowners.

Despite the presence of access to preferential loans from KfW, retrofitting is still too expensive for private homeowners to cover all the cost. Very few owners have the necessary capital to self-fund retrofit projects. The cost of retrofitting varies hugely among houses. Homeowners do not even know how much whole house retrofits would cost. The perception that the value of retrofit is less than its cost can make it extremely difficult to induce a homeowner to participate in retrofitting. It also means that homeowners may choose to undertake only the energy efficiency measures, which are financially most attractive. This in turn means that properties could be retrofitted to a level that is less than their potential, and that it could become more difficult to justify the cost of deeper measures in the future, thereby making it harder to meet long term energy saving and carbon reduction targets.

4.2 Energy performance is not reflected in property value.

Energy performance is not currently reflected in property value (in both the rental and sales market) and Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) are not displayed at point of sale. This discourage private homeowners to retrofit since they cannot see increase in their property value after retrofitting. However, housing market is believed to become more sophisticated and place greater value on energy efficiency and to equate an energy efficient home with a high quality home, the driver for retrofit could become the increased market value. This value could translate itself into homes, which sell faster, earn higher sales premiums or can attract higher loan-to-value mortgages. The property value should also take into account of comfort levels, health benefits, not just energy bill savings.

4.3 The landlord/tenant dilemma.

The rented sector suffers from the “landlord/tenant dilemma” problem whereby the tenant benefits from retrofit or energy efficiency measures that are paid for by the housing owner. The return of retrofitting for house owners is often achieved by increasing rent, which is difficult to calculate and may weaken their houses renting market competency. Also, vacancy of property during retrofitting is not affordable for private owners as they rely on rents. Therefore, at present there is little incentive for the owner to undertake retrofit, particularly without proof that it will increase the value of the property.

4.4 Long payback period and low return on investment.

From the perspective of investors, financial returns and risks of retrofitting are unclear. In a typical investment scenario, initial costs are offset over time by increasing revenue streams. However, in the case of retrofitting, costs are typically offset by calculated savings rather than quantifiable revenue streams. Estimated avoided cost is not equivalent to a revenue stream, making access to finance a challenge. In terms of funding, although there are banks and investment funds interested in supporting retrofitting, few programs have developed funding offers that are standardized, replicable and scalable. This standardization is essential to reduce transaction costs and increase the number of projects. For private homeowners, it is difficult to achieve scale economy and leverage private-sector investment. Few programs have been able to achieve the volume of transactions needed to secure significant financing amounts with low cost of capital.

4.5 Credit unworthiness of homeowners.

Homeowners who have already retired face credit worthiness issues, as they are no longer earning money. Their capital reserves are too small to finance energy efficient retrofit and government subsidies and funding programs are not sufficient to cover the cost. The long payback period also discourage investors to invest on old families. While for young family, their main concerns are financing to purchase houses rather than energy efficient retrofit.

5. EXISTING RETROFIT FINANCING SCHEMES IN GERMANY

The German Development Bank (KfW) is the main financing institution implementing policies in buildings and other energy-related sectors in Germany. Since 1996, KfW has been providing preferential loans and grants to increase thermal retrofit investments in the residential sector. The bank offers two main programs: “Energy Efficient Renovation” (Energieeffizient Sanieren) for retrofitting and “Energy Efficient Construction” (Energieeffizient Bauen) for new construction; especially to support energy efficiency investment in the residential sector. In addition, there are differences in funding terms between comprehensive retrofitting (whole house approach) and single measure retrofitting. A comprehensive retrofitting project is funded more generously than individual measures or a combination of individual measures.

Various financing packages are available in the form of either loans or grants determined by the targeted energy standard. Maximum levels of repayment bonuses, grant equivalents of loans, and grants provided by KfW depend on the levels of achieved building energy performance. The low interest loans are offered to cover project costs for a value of up to 75,000 Euros per residential unit together with repayment bonuses, and maximum 50,000 Euros per housing unit for individual or combined measures without a bonus. The repayment periods of the loans range from 10 – 30 years.

The grant subsidies are available for both comprehensive and single measure retrofitting. A grant is defined as a percentage of total project cost. Similar principles also considered as the loan programs. However, grants are only available to owners of 1-2 family homes (max. 2 housing units), to purchasers of newly refurbished 1-2 family units, and to owner-occupied co-operatives.

Access to loans is available to homeowners, landlords, as well as purchasers of newly refurbished residential units including individuals, housing companies, housing co-operatives, municipalities, district bodies, community groups and other public or non-profit bodies.

In terms of application, grants applications (available independently of an applicant’s income) are made directly to KfW. In order to be eligible for these ‘Efficiency House’ grants, a certificate from an approved energy adviser is needed, and the retrofitting work has to be

undertaken by paid workers and meet the technical requirements of the program. KfW subsidies cannot be combined with other loan programs subsidised by federal or regional governments.

On the other hand, KfW does not directly handle with the loan applications. A network of local financial institutions is employed for the processing of applications, loans and repayments, and to help borrowers. KfW also offers a special program for applicants who fail to meet the demanding requirements of the government-sponsored KfW programs. This loan program is not as substantial because the qualifying conditions for borrowers are less stringent (KfW, 2010c).

It can be seen that KfW programs are attractive to private homeowners who would like to perform energy efficient retrofitting on their age-old residences. These national programs combine several financing measures, which may not be specifically designed to suit a city-level context. Moreover, since there are a number of funding measures which require separate application processes, and the loan application process is quite complicated, it may be more effective to devise a new special purpose vehicle (SPV) to deliver financial support particularly to private homeowners tailored to the local context of a city.

6. SOME LESSONS FROM OTHER EU COUNTRIES

Since 2007, Italian government has provided tax credit incentive for energy efficiency retrofitting. Both single measure retrofits including thermal insulation and replacement of heating systems, and comprehensive building retrofit can benefit from this scheme. More than half (55%) of the energy-related costs can be recovered through this tax incentive but the total amount cannot be more than the values differentiated by the types of retrofit measure, for example not exceed USD 139,430 for comprehensive retrofit which reduce energy demand at least 20% lower than the current building code. The 10-year period of tax credit reimbursement begins after the retrofitting is completed. Investment in retrofitting the residential sector saw a significant increase. In 2009, 240,000 tax credit claims were submitted. However, in France, a similar tax credit scheme may not work as expected since a survey of home owners reported that 51% of them did not make the retrofitting decisions based on the tax incentive (Mure, 2010 cited in Neuhoff et al, 2012).

In the Netherlands, even though tax credit programs for retrofits in the residential sector do not exist, since 1997 energy efficiency and renewable energy tax deductions have been available to all sectors under the Energy Investment Allowance (EIA). For qualified energy efficient and renewable energy technologies, tax deductions can cover up to 41.5% of the investment cost. Therefore both single measures and comprehensive retrofit in the building sector can apply. Nevertheless, comprehensive measures must improve energy efficiency by at least two energy classes or labels (NL Agency, 2011). In addition, the Energies pong program (Energy Jump) was established in 2009 to generate a large scale demand and supply for zero-energy houses and buildings (E-0 houses) since the technologies and materials for that are readily available. A new financial arrangement was developed for the private homeowners on the basis that an average household in the Netherlands pays €2,200 per annum for energy bills. So this amount of money is saved when the house is retrofitted to zero energy consumption. It is calculated that the savings will be about 9 billion euros if there are 4 million houses participating in retrofitting. Then this sum of money is available for financing the retrofitting projects. After completion, homeowners will pay back the same amount of the energy bill saved to the financing institution. Moreover, since this is a recurring process, so the revenue stream for the investment can be used to finance more projects.

7. Our proposal: retroFrank-SPV

7.1 Financing Scheme for Retrofitting Private houses in Frankfurt

The financing scheme is designed in such a way that homeowners achieve retrofitting by not using their own money and by not affecting their disposable income. The City Council provides upfront subsidy to homeowners who do retrofitting. The rest of the funding needed for retrofitting is provided by the private sector through retroFrank fund.

The Frankfurt City Council sets up a green fund. We name it retroFrank fund. This fund sells bonds to private investors and collects fund, and then provide loans to homeowners for retrofitting.

To incentivise homeowners to apply for a loan from this fund, the City Council will provide subsidies to homeowners (Box 2). The subsidy takes the form of upfront grant, which increases with the energy efficiency ratio achieved. The more energy saving ratio homeowners achieve through retrofitting, the more subsidy they can get from the City Council.

Box 2: The retroFrank retrofit grant scheme

Energy efficiency ratio achieved (%)	80	60	40	20	10
Grant (%) of total retrofitting cost	50	40	30	20	10

As the sponsor of retroFrank fund, the Frankfurt City Council will act as an intermediary to bridge the homeowners and long term investors. As a pilot program, the retroFrank fund will collect 10 million Euros: 2 million from the City Council, and the remaining 8 million from private investors. The City Council's 2 million Euros will act as equity of the fund, and take the first loss.

Figure 2: Diagram of proposed financial model called “retroFrank”

Source: Authors draft

The fund will sell bonds to long term investors, like life insurers and pension funds. Those who invest in this fund will be recognized as green investor by the City Council and hence awarded with Green Investor Certificates. The return of bonds will be set at a competitive level given their risks. Due to low credit risk and the City Council’s investment of 2 million Euros in this fund, the private investors bear very little default risk.

Homeowners pay back the loan by saved energy bill; the benefit they receive through reduced hospitalization, reduced days off work, and reduced days off school due to improved living conditions; appreciation in property value. The payment of each individual homeowner will range between the energy bill saved, and 3 times as large as the energy bill saved. This is based on a recent study that the total benefit to homeowners is about four times as large as the energy bill saved (Chapman et al, 2009).

This payment in each period is designed to reflect the average benefit the homeowner receives from retrofitting. Because the marginal cost of retrofitting is increasing in energy saving ratio, so a general repayment schedule is: the higher energy saving ratio you achieve through retrofitting, the larger the loan will be, the longer it will take to repay the loan for homeowners. A general payback schedule is like the following.

Box 2: The retroFrank retrofit grant scheme

Energy efficiency ratio (%)	80	60	40	20	10
Repayment period (years)	50	40	30	20	10

7.2 Specify a Targeted Homeowners Group

Our financing scheme is targeted at old buildings built from 1949 to 1968 in Frankfurt. The project could be scaled up and cover all old buildings in Frankfurt in its second phase, but we decided to limit the scope of the first phase to the above-mentioned category of buildings for the following reasons. First, these kinds of houses are not in a good condition, and needs to be renovated anyway. Retrofitting is also another kind of renovation.

If the government puts forward attractive financing scheme, this group of homeowners will have stronger incentive to do retrofitting. Second, we would like to make our project simple and straightforward. The retroFrank fund has only 10 million Euros and it cannot cover all old buildings in Frankfurt. The project we proposed is at most a pilot program, which can be implemented easily. If it has to cover all old buildings in Frankfurt, 10 million is probably inadequate, and would require the burdensome task of soliciting more funds.

7.3 Solving the landlord and tenant dilemma

Under the provision of existing German rent control law- as of November 2013, (i) rents must not rise by any more 20 percent in three years. First year rent is rise free. (ii) Newly built houses exempted from such restrictions.

The possible solution regarding the compliance of Retrofitted houses with rent control Law could as follows – (i) Get retrofitted houses legally treated as newly built houses. (ii) The rise in rent will be set at a level which can be largely offset by the decrease in energy bill and hospitalization cost, and off school, off work cost. (iii) The overall cost of living in rented retrofitted houses keeps on the similar level as before retrofitting.

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